

No larval parasitization was found in larvae reared in the laboratory.

Sesamia larvae were more numerous in wheat fields than in other cropping systems, but no infestation on wheat was recorded.

Larval mortality was higher (30%) in conventional-tillage wheat fields than in no-tillage wheat fields (7%). However, there were more live larvae in no-tillage wheat fields (Table 2).

Part of the reason for low rice yields in Pakistan may be high SB carryover. ■

Table 2. Survival of SB larvae in no-tillage and conventional tillage wheat in Sindh, India.

Location	Larval density/m							
	No tillage				Conventional tillage			
	Live (no.)	Dead (no.)	Mortality (%)	Tiller infestation (%)	Live (no.)	Dead (no.)	Mortality (%)	Tiller infestation (%)
Jamra I (Shikarpur)	15	1	6	42.15	10	5	33	48.82
Jamra II (Shikarpur)	39	2	5	47.01	32	10	28	46.67
Dokri (Larkana)	14	1	7	24.09	3	1	25	8.97
Arija (Larkana)	33	4	11	27.10	17	8	32	17.51
Mean	25	2	7	35.09	16	6	30	30.49

Cropping patterns for Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

Nguyen Van Dan and Dang Kim Son, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute, Omon Haugiang, Vietnam

In the Cuu Long Delta, favorable rainfall and river water level patterns make double-cropped rice the normal practice on alluvial soils near the Hau and Tien Rivers. We thought it possible to grow three crops a year, using short-duration rice varieties and relay cropping in a *sa ngam* method of crop establishment (seeds broadcast on soil flooded 20-30 cm deep, 7-12 d before complete water subsidence).

We compared two cropping patterns—rice - soybean + rice and rice - mungbean - rice—with the existing farmers' pattern of rice - rice during 1987-88 wet (WS) and dry seasons (DS) in Thuanhung, Haugiang (see figure).

Soil of the experimental field had 3.21% organic C and 0.22% N, 0.068% P, and 1.842% K. Available P was 11.0 mg/100 g. Varieties used were rice IR64, soybean MTD65, and mungbean DX102. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications.

DS rice was planted by *sa ngam* method 22 Nov 1987 and harvested 5 Mar 1988. DS soybean and mungbean were sown 10 Mar 1988 and harvested 29 and 15 May 1988, respectively. WS rice was broadcast 16 May 1988 (13 d before harvesting soybean), without

Average grain and rice equivalent yield, and economic efficiency of 3 cropping patterns. Thuanhung, Vietnam, 1987-88.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)			Rice equivalent yield (t/ha)	Labor cost (t/ha)	Material and power costs (S/ha)	Total cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
	Crop 1 DS rice	Crop 2 soybean or mungbean	Crop 3 WS rice					
DS rice - DS soybean + WS rice	6.4	2.4	3.7	17.3	268.0	213.1	482.3	444.5
DS rice - DS mungbean + WS rice	6.3	1.3	3.2	15.2	244.8	237.3	183.4	330.4
DS rice - WS rice	6.4		2.8	9.3	92.2	175.3	267.7	230.5

tillage. Recommended fertilizer rates were used: 100 kg N + 40 kg P on rice, 60 kg N + 60 kg P on soybean, and 40 kg N + 60 kg P on mungbean.

Grain yield of WS rice differed significantly with cropping pattern (see table). The pattern with soybean produced the highest rice equivalent yield

(17.3 t/ha). Lowest yield (9.3 t/ha) was with two crops of rice.

This pattern also had the lowest cost (US\$92.2/ha), especially for labor. Total costs of triple cropping were about double that of two rice crops.

Net return of rice - soybean + rice was highest (US\$444.5/ha). ■

Rainfall and water level pattern, and cropping pattern in Thuanhung, Haugiang, Vietnam.